

A Descriptive Study to Assess the Knowledge Regarding Menopausal Symptoms and its Management Among Women in Selected Community of Rewa (M.P.)

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Abstract:- The word Menopause derives from a Greek word. 'Guys' which potential 'Month' and 'Pauses' which ability 'Cessation' (Leon 1990). As a result, Menopause refers to everlasting cessation of menstruation at the end of reproductive lifestyles due to ovarian follicular state of no activity. Growing older is a fact of life and its miles a normal method of getting brittle bones, sagging pores and pores and skin and degenerating body features. In getting older women, they'll additionally experience a popularly acknowledged state of affairs known as menopause. This is characterized by way of manner of adjustments that show up in a lady's existence earlier than and her menstruation ends signaling her infertility years.

➤ Research Methodology

A descriptive survey lookup strategy used to be viewed the first-class to examine the know-how concerning menopausal signs and its administration amongst female in the current learn about the non-experimental lookup plan was once viewed the most appropriate via the investigator. In non-experimental research, researchers gather information besides making adjustments or introducing treatments. Data got are analyzed and the consequences may also lead to the formation of speculation than can be examined experimentally. Non-probability Convenient sampling method will be used for the study. Non-probability Convenient sampling method makes use of individuals who are with ease handy to the researcher and meet the standards for the study.

➤ Result

Data introduced in Table no. 4.1 exhibits that most of the issue 24 had been in the team of 40-45 years, 20.0 p.c had been between the age team of forty six to 50 years, 18.3 p.c had been in the age team of 51-55 years and the ultimate 21.7 percent have been in the age team of > fifty five years. With regards to education, most of the topics 36.6 p.c had studied up to the middle, 26.7% every had fundamental and secondary and 10.0 percent had studied up to graduation. 71.7 percent of the pattern lived in a nuclear household and

the closing 28.3 percent lived in nuclear families. Regarding the profits of the household forty five percent of the pattern had an profits of Rs 20000 and above, 21.7 p.c had profits beneath Rs 5000 and 20 percent had earnings between Rs ten thousand - 20000 and 13.3 percent of the pattern had profits between Rs 5000 - ten thousand Concerning faith 68.3 p.c of the populace was once Hindu and 26.7 p.c of the populace used to be Muslim and 3.3 percent of the populace used to be Christian and the ultimate 1.7 p.c of the populace used to be of any other religions. The mass media publicity used to be ordinarily 83.4 p.c of newspapers or magazines, 8.3 percent used to be of every radio and from different sources and none of the topics bought facts from television.

➤ Conclusion

From the findings of the learn about it is clear that the female had a terrible information related to menopausal signs and symptoms and its administration and additionally the learn about decided the no affiliation between understanding rating and demographic variables. There is a want to instruct the ladies related to the menopausal signs and its management, nurses have a pivotal function in fitness promoting and imparting expertise related to menopausal signs and symptoms and its administration and its sick results each in health facility and neighborhood settings.

1. The existing find out about printed that the female have negative expertise related to menopausal signs and symptoms and its management.
2. There is no sizeable affiliation between know-how rating and demographic variables.

I. INTRODUCTION

The word menopause derives from a Greek word. 'guys' which potential 'month' and 'pauses' which ability 'cessation' (Leon 1990). As a result, menopause refers to everlasting cessation of menstruation at the end of reproductive lifestyles due to ovarian follicular state of no activity. Growing older is a fact of life and it's miles a normal method of getting brittle

bones, sagging pores and pores and skin and degenerating body features. In getting older women, they'll additionally experience a popularly acknowledged state of affairs known as menopause. This is characterized by way of manner of adjustments that show up in a lady's existence earlier than and her menstruation ends signaling her infertility years. usually, an man or woman woman has finite range of eggs, which are determined in her ovaries. The ovaries secrete hormones, together with oestrogen and progesterone. Such hormones are responsible in regulating menstruation and ovulation. As ladies become old, menopause outcomes as the ovaries can now not launch an egg every month and the ordinary menstruation cycle. adjustments in fitness and sickness of individuals create a way of transition, and client in transition duration will be inclined to be extra liable to be dangers that would also in flip have an impact on their health, uncovering these risks may additionally be extra fantastic by manner of appreciation the transition manner. Menopause can also be visible as a transition from middle age to historic age and girls fear this length because of the truth of the expected losses. Even though menopause is a frequent experience for ladies but the ride is now not regular (Mc grow 1990). There may be no steady sample and no chain of occasions that need to transpire. The onset and give up are unpredictable. The duration

is indefinite and the stories are specific for every and each lady as she passes thru it. These days, fitness tool has defined their plans based totally on the family's health. girls are regarded because the base of own family's fitness which further to health administration of household members, are unique patterns of coaching and propagating a wholesome life style to the following generation. Women have a higher populace and their average age of existence expectancy is more and they face awesome issues ensuing from their herbal and physiological prerequisites this sort of troubles is the menopausal transitional period or closing years of pregnancy.

II. STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

“A descriptive study to assess the knowledge regarding menopausal symptoms and its management among women in selected community of Rewa (M. P.)”

Objectives of the study -

1. To assess the knowledge regarding menopausal symptoms and its management among women.
2. To determine the association of knowledge with the selected demographic variables.

Table1:- Description of demographic variables of women by using percentage analysis.

S. No.	Selected Demographic Variable	Frequency Total	Percentage %
1	Age in years <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 40-45 years • 46-50 years • 51-55 years • > 55 years 	24 12 11 13	40.0 20.0 18.3 21.7
2	Educational Status <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Primary • Middle • Higher Secondary • Graduate and above 	16 22 16 6	26.7 36.6 26.7 10.0
3	Type of Family <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Nuclear • Joint 	43 17	71.7 28.3
4	Family Income per Month (Rs) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <Rs 5000 • 5000-10000 • 10000-20000 • >Rs 20000 	13 8 12 27	21.7 13.3 20.0 45.0
5	Religion <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Hindu • Muslim • Christian • Any other 	41 16 2 1	68.3 26.7 3.3 1.7
6	Mass Media Exposure <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Radio • Television • Newspaper/ Magazine • Others if any 	5 0 50 5	8.3 0 83.4 8.3

Table 2:- Pretest knowledge score of the sample (n = 60)

Pre-test knowledge score	Pretest	
	Frequency	Percentage
21-30 (Good)	0	0
11-20 (Average)	12	20.0
0-10 (Poor)	48	80.0
Total	60	100%

Pre-test mean score is = 8.21

S. D. = 3.09

Result indicates that 80% of the pattern had a very negative know-how rating ranging between 0-10 and 20% samples had common expertise rating ranging between 11-20 involving the menopausal signs and its administration and none of the topics had a correct know-how involving menopausal signs and its management.

Table 3:- Chi-square cost displaying the affiliation between pretest know-how rating and chosen demographic variables (N = 60)

S. No.	Variables	POOR	AVERAGE	GOOD	Total	Chi square value	df	P value	Inference
1	AGE					2.597	3	.458	NS
	40-45 year	19	5	0	24				
	46-50 year	8	4	0	12				
	51- 55 year	9	2	0	11				
	> 55 year	12	1	0	13				
2	TYPE OF FAMILY					.185	1	.667	NS
	Nuclear	35	8	0	43				
	Joint	13	4	0	17				
3	RELIGION					1.845	3	.605	NS
	Hindu	34	7	0	41				
	Muslim	12	4	0	16				
	Christian	1	1	0	2				
	Specify If any	1	0	0	1				
4	Education status					1.868	3	.600	NS
	Graduation	6	0	0	6				
	Secondary	13	3	0	16				
	Middle	17	5	0	22				
	Primary	12	4	0	16				
5	Monthly Income of family (In rupees)					.465	3	.927	NS
	<Rs 5000	11	2	0	13				
	5000-10000	6	2	0	8				
	Rs 10000-20000	10	2	0	12				
	>Rs 20000	21	6	0	27				
6	Use of Knowledgeable Resources					1.375	2	.503	NS
	Radio	4	1	0	5				
	Television	0	0	0	0				
	Newspaper	41	9	0	50				
	Specific if any	3	2	0	5				

*= Not significance at < .000 level

**= Significant at < .000 level

The data in desk four. three depicted the computed chi-square values between pretest expertise rating and the demographic variables indicated that there is no big affiliation between age, instructional reputation, type of family, profits, faith and mass media exposure. subsequently, research hypothesis H1 changed into rejected precis This bankruptcy has handled the evaluation and interpretation of statistics amassed from 60 girls of selected network i.e. Laxmanpur community,

Rewa. Descriptive and inferential statistics were used for analysis. The Pre-check mean rating changed into 8.21. Majority of the women had negative level of know-how concerning menopausal symptoms and its management. there was no association between understanding with decided on demographic variables. dependent Variable inside the gift take a look at based variable refers to the understanding of women regarding the menopausal signs and symptoms and its

management. This take a look at made use of a descriptive approach with a non-experimental studies design. The population of the have a look at consisted of ladies of decided on network i.e. Laxmanpur community, Rewa. Non-chance convenient sampling method became applied to choose 60 girls based on positive predetermined standards.

The investigator prepared a dependent information questionnaire together with 30 questions to assess the information of women. 10 experts did the validation of the tools. Pre-testing and reliability of device had been hooked up prior to the pilot take a look at. The reliability of the device become located to be $r = 0.81$. A pilot take a look at was conducted on 10 girls, this offers a foundation for the investigator to conduct the primary observe. the principle study turned into carried out on 60 ladies of Laxmanpur network, Rewa. The duration of the take a look at became from sixteen September to 23 September 2021. Samples had been decided on via Non-possibility convenient sampling technique; structured understanding questionnaire turned into used to acquire statistics. Then the pre-check became performed using a dependent knowledge questionnaire. The facts obtained have been analyzed in phrases of the objectives and speculation the usage of descriptive and inferential information. The findings of the take a look at proved that the women have inadequate knowledge concerning the menopausal symptoms and its management. The mean pre-check information score become 8.21.

III. MAIN FINDINGS

The findings of the study found out that:

- Majority of the subjects forty% had been inside the age institution of forty-45 years.
- Majority of the subjects 36.6% had been educated as much as the middle.
- Majority of the subject's seventy one.7% had been residing in nuclear families.
- regarding the income of the family 45% of the pattern had an profits of Rs > 20000.
- Majority of the subject's 68.three% of ladies of childbearing age belonged to Hindu religion
- With reference to mass media exposure the majority of the samples had been getting information from newspaper.

➤ *Pre-test knowledge score of women concerning Menopausal signs and its control:*

Desk four.2and determine 4.7 shows that 80% of the sample had a very poor information score ranging between zero-10 and 20% samples had common understanding score ranging among eleven-20 concerning the menopausal signs and its control and not one of the subjects had an amazing know-how concerning menopausal signs and symptoms and its control.

➤ *Relationship of information with decided on demographic variables:*

The statistics depicted the computed chi-square values among pretest know-how rating and the demographic variables indicated that there's no great affiliation between age, educational reput, sort of circle of relatives, income, religion and mass media publicity with information.

IV. CONCLUSION

From the findings of the take a look at it's miles clean that the women had a negative information concerning menopausal signs and its management and additionally the look at determined the no affiliation among know-how rating and demographic variables.

There's a want to educate the girls regarding the menopausal signs and its control, nurses have a pivotal position in fitness merchandising and presenting expertise concerning menopausal signs and symptoms and its management and its unwell results each in medical institution and community settings.

1. The present look at found out that the ladies have terrible know-how regarding menopausal signs and its management.
2. There is no vast affiliation among know-how score and demographic variables.

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